

Efficient Polyline Smoothing with G^1 Continuity and Curvature Constraints for Shortest Path

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Abstract—In this paper, we present an efficient algorithm for smoothing polylines in vehicle motion planning with curvature constraints. The method is tailored to generate paths that meet specific requirements: 1) minimal length, 2) G^1 continuity with bounded curvature, and 3) guaranteed collision-free properties, under mild assumptions. We compare our approach with existing state-of-the-art techniques, highlighting its benefits in terms of both computational efficiency and path length optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we introduce the Dubins Path Smoothing (DPS) algorithm, a novel approach designed for rapid polyline smoothing using a sequence of motion primitives that ensure G^1 continuity and bounded curvature.

The main contributions of the paper are as follows: 1) the length of the smoothed path is upper bounded by the length of the original polyline; 2) under certain assumptions, if the polyline is collision-free, the smoothed path is also guaranteed to be collision-free; 3) the solution is robust: removing segments from the path does not affect the remaining sections; 4) we show the optimality of the smoothed path; 5) as the path consists of straight segments and circular arcs of prescribed radius, offsetting the path preserves its properties.

The problem of determining the shortest G^1 -continuous path between an initial and final position, with specified initial and final orientations and a fixed minimum turning radius, is referred to as the Markov-Dubins path [2].

A generalization of this problem, where the goal is to interpolate multiple points, is known as the Multi-Point Markov-Dubins Problem (MPMDP). Several studies have addressed this, such as optimal control formulations [5], which, although being computationally intensive, yield highly accurate solutions. A sampling-based method is introduced in [4], where dynamic programming and iterative refinements are used to find a solution.

Regarding polyline smoothing, a method similar to ours was proposed in [10], where the authors present an algorithm with $O(n^2)$ complexity to smooth the polyline by first identifying maximum convex subsections and then approximating them with curves.

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II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this section, we state the problem we are focusing on and show that thanks to Bellman's principle of optimality, it is possible to consider, without loss of generality, a sub-problem of it, which is more easily solved.

Definition 1 (Polyline). A polyline $P = (p_0, p_1, \dots, p_{n-1})$ is an ordered sequence of $n > 2$ points $p_j = (x_j, y_j) \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

Assumption 1 (Conditions on the polyline). Any triplet of consecutive points p_{j-1}, p_j, p_{j+1} of the polyline P is not-aligned, and, given a scenario with obstacles, the polyline P is collision-free w.r.t. the obstacles by design.

We consider scenarios in which the obstacles are inflated in order to avoid them and provide collision-free polylines. Later, we will provide a lower bound on how much the obstacles should be inflated to ensure the smoothed path is collision-free.

Definition 2 (Problem). Let P be a collision-free polyline. The goal is to find a feasible path \mathcal{P} approximating the polyline P with a shortest path for a non-holonomic robot subject to a minimum turning radius r , with G^1 continuity.

We define the angles $\theta_j = \text{atan2}(y_{j+1} - y_j, x_{j+1} - x_j)$, for $j < n-1$, as the direction between point p_j and point p_{j+1} , and $\alpha_j = \pi - (\theta_j - \theta_{j-1})$ as the internal angle between $\overrightarrow{p_{j-1}p_j}$ and $\overrightarrow{p_j p_{j+1}}$. Since tackling the smoothing of the whole polyline P can be challenging, we can consider, without loss of generality, the sub-problem in which we want to construct the shortest path with G^1 continuity and bounded curvature to smooth a polyline composed of 3 non-aligned points, p_i, p_m, p_f (respectively initial, middle and final points). To solve this problem, a circle of fixed radius r , equal to the turning radius of the robot, is constructed tangent to the

Figure 1: Visual representation of 3-points sub-problem.

two lines defined by the polyline, as shown in Figure 1. This intersection defines the tangent points q_{m_1} and q_{m_2} in proximity of point p_m . The obtained path is formed by line and arcs interpolating $Q = (p_i, q_{m_1}, q_{m_2}, p_f)$, as in Figure 1. The designed path is feasible for a non-holonomic robot by construction. In order for this approximation to exist, the segments between the points of P must be long enough to contain the tangent points in the correct order. For instance, considering Figure 1, the segment $\overline{p_m p_f}$ must be longer than the segment $\overline{q_{m_2} p_f}$. Next, we will formalize these requirements in precise terms.

III. SOLUTION FORMALIZATION

In this section, we focus on formalizing the 3-points sub-problem and presenting a solution to it. To simplify the explanation, we begin by applying a translation and a rotation to the initial configuration of the points, without loss of generality. First, we translate the points by shifting the coordinates of p_i so that it moves to the origin. Then, we rotate the system using a rotation $R(\varphi)$ to align the point p_m along the positive x-axis. If the point p_f is positioned below the x-axis (i.e., $y_f < 0$), we reflect it across the x-axis, ensuring that we are always considering positive coordinates, more details in [7].

One important condition that needs to be met for the solution to exist involves the configuration of the points. Consider a polyline $P = (p_i, p_m, p_f)$ formed by three non-aligned points, with α_m representing the angle at p_m . To ensure the existence of a smooth G^1 -continuous approximation of this polyline, there is a necessary constraint that the distances between consecutive points must satisfy. Specifically, the distance between the points must be large enough in relation to the turning radius r of the path:

$$\min(\|p_m - p_i\|, \|p_f - p_m\|) \geq \frac{r}{\tan(\alpha_m/2)} \quad (1)$$

This constraint can be extended to the entire polyline. In the general case, when considering the whole polyline P , we also must ensure that the tangent points in the segment $\overline{p_j p_k}$ exist and are consecutive, that is, $\|p_j - q_{j_2}\| \leq \|p_j - q_{k_1}\|$ and $\|p_k - q_{k_1}\| \leq \|p_k - q_{j_2}\|$.

In particular, the distance $\|p_j - p_k\|$ must satisfy:

$$\|p_j - p_k\| \geq \left| \frac{r}{\tan(\alpha_j/2)} \right| + \left| \frac{r}{\tan(\alpha_k/2)} \right|. \quad (2)$$

When these conditions are met, it is possible to determine the tangent points between the path and the segments formed by the points. These tangent points q_{j_1} and q_{j_2} are:

$$q_{j_1} = p_j - l_j \hat{v}_{j_1}, \quad q_{j_2} = p_j + l_j \hat{v}_{j_2}, \quad (3)$$

where \hat{v}_{j_1} , \hat{v}_{j_2} are the direction from p_{j-1} to p_j , and from p_j to p_{j+1} , respectively. The distance l_j between p_j and q_{j_1} is defined in Algorithm 1, which runs in constant time.

On the complexity of the algorithm. The computation for each individual segment of the path can be done in constant time. Since the polyline P consists of $n - 1$ segments (for n points), the total complexity of computing

Algorithm 1 The pseudo-code to compute the i^{th} piece of the path \mathcal{P} (i.e., Q_i), in the general case.

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1: function SOLVE_3_POINTS( $p_i = (x_i, y_i)$ ,  $p_m = (x_m, y_m)$ ,
    $p_f = (x_f, y_f)$ )
2:    $v_1 \leftarrow [x_m - x_i, y_m - y_i]^T$ ,    $v_2 \leftarrow [x_f - x_m, y_f - y_m]^T$ 
3:    $\hat{v}_1 \leftarrow v_1 / \|v_1\|$ ,    $\hat{v}_2 \leftarrow v_2 / \|v_2\|$ 
4:    $l = r \frac{\|v_1 \times v_2\|}{(v_1 \cdot v_2) + \|v_1\| \|v_2\|}$ 
5:    $q_{m_1} \leftarrow p_m - l \hat{v}_1$ ,    $q_{m_2} \leftarrow p_m + l \hat{v}_2$ 
6:    $Q \leftarrow \{p_i q_{m_1} + q_{m_1} q_{m_2}\}$ 
7: return  $Q$ 

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all the segments is proportional to n . This results in an overall linear complexity of $\Theta(n)$.

Corollary 1 (Distance from the polyline points). *The path Q has distance D_j from the intermediate point p_j of the polyline P (see Figure 1), given by:*

$$D_j = d - r = r \left(\frac{1}{\sin(\alpha_m/2)} - 1 \right) = r \cdot \text{excsc}(\alpha_m/2) \quad (4)$$

Assumption 2 (Minimum distance between points). *Let r be the minimum turning radius of the robot, p_j and p_k two consecutive points of the polyline P and q_{k_2} the first tangent point after p_k . We assume that the points p_j and q_{k_2} have a distance of at least $4r$, i.e., $\|p_j - q_{k_2}\| \geq 4r$.*

Given the previous assumptions, we can show that the generated path Q is a Dubins path, i.e., the shortest one of bounded curvature and G^1 continuity. Consequently, the overall path \mathcal{P} , formed by concatenating the individual segments of Q , is the shortest possible solution that maintains the required smoothness and proximity to the original polyline P . Furthermore, it also holds that the path \mathcal{P} is shorter than the polyline P .

In practical applications, when dealing with motion planning problems in environments with obstacles, it is important to ensure that the path remains collision-free. To achieve this, one can apply a mitered offset [6] to the obstacles, inflating them by a sufficient amount to guarantee clearance for the robot's movement. The required offset is given by the following formula:

$$O = \max \left(h \sin \frac{\alpha_m}{2} + r \left(1 - \sin \frac{\alpha_m}{2} \right), h \right). \quad (5)$$

where h is the radius of the robot.

Note that the obstacles in the map are assumed to be convex. Otherwise, their convex hull can be employed.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present an experimental evaluation of the proposed algorithm. The experiments were conducted on a desktop computer with an Intel i9-10940X processor and an Nvidia RTX A5000 GPU, running Ubuntu 22.04.

a) *Path Interpolation:* In this experiment, we aim to demonstrate the performance gains of our algorithm over the state-of-the-art methods [3], [1] in terms of both computation time and the lengths of the approximated

Figure 2: Results of the interpolation test

paths during interpolation. To achieve this, we fit $N = 10^i$, $i = 1, \dots, 6$ randomly sampled points and repeat the tests 1000 times. The points are sampled ensuring to meet the requirements of Section III.

We evaluate our algorithm against two state-of-the-art methods: the Open Motion Planning Library (OMPL) [9] and the iterative MPDP algorithm [4], which uses dynamic programming to interpolate multiple points with Dubins paths. The following key distinctions between our approach and these algorithms are highlighted:

- OMPL does not natively support interpolation through multiple points. To address this, we use our Dubins Path Smoothing (DPS) algorithm to compute intermediate points q_i and angles θ_i , which are then used by OMPL to interpolate the path using Dubins maneuvers.
- MPDP is a sampling-based algorithm focused on precisely interpolating points by optimizing the angles to ensure that the final path passes through each point. In contrast, our algorithm seeks shorter paths that do not necessarily pass through the points but maintain a bounded distance and G^1 curvature continuity.

We test and compare two versions of our algorithm: sequential and parallel. The parallel version uses CUDA, exploiting the fact that paths between triplets of points can be computed independently.

Figure 2 shows that our algorithm, both in its sequential (DPS-Seq) and parallel (DPS-Par) versions, outperforms OMPL in computation time by approximately one order of magnitude and MPDP by two orders of magnitude.

We also compare our algorithm with the biarcs approach [1], which shares similarities with our G^1 curve smoothing but does not enforce curvature constraints.

b) Road Maps: In this experiment, we assess the performance of our DPS algorithm in computing a feasible path using a visibility graph on maps with obstacles sourced from [8]. The process begins by constructing a visibility road map based on the vertices of the inflated obstacles. We then apply the A* algorithm to find the shortest path on this road map, followed by smoothing the path with DPS. For comparison, we evaluate our approach against MPDP, which requires the extracted polyline as input, and

Figure 3: Results of the roadmap test

OMPL, which needs the tangent points and their angles, as in previous comparisons. The experiments were conducted using 10,000 different pairs of points to allow for statistical analysis. In Figure 3, the results indicate that even with a small number of points, our algorithm significantly outperforms the competitors. Additionally, the paths generated by our method are guaranteed to be feasible for traversal.

V. CONCLUSION

We have presented DPS, a fast algorithm to generate the shortest smooth approximation of a polyline with G^1 continuity and bounded curvature. This approach comes with a series of important proved properties, i.e. proofs and conditions on existence, optimality, feasibility, and bounded distance, enabling not only to find an optimal approximation for the path, but also to ensure the quality of such path.

REFERENCES

- [1] Enrico Bertolazzi and Marco Frego. A Note on Robust Biarc Computation. *Computer-Aided Design and Applications*, 16(5):822–835, 2019.
- [2] L. E. Dubins. On Curves of Minimal Length with a Constraint on Average Curvature, and with Prescribed Initial and Terminal Positions and Tangents. *American Journal of Mathematics*, 79(3):497–516, 1957.
- [3] Marco Frego, Paolo Bevilacqua, Stefano Divan, Fabiano Zenatti, Luigi Palopoli, Francesco Biral, and Daniele Fontanelli. Minimum time—Minimum jerk optimal traffic management for AGVs. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 5(4):5307–5314, 2020.
- [4] Marco Frego, Paolo Bevilacqua, Enrico Saccon, Luigi Palopoli, and Daniele Fontanelli. An Iterative Dynamic Programming Approach to the Multipoint Markov-Dubins Problem. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 5(2):2483–2490, 2020.
- [5] C Yalçın Kaya. Markov-dubins interpolating curves. *Computational Optimization and Applications*, 73(2):647–677, 2019.
- [6] Sang C. Park and Yun C. Chung. Mitered offset for profile machining. *Computer-Aided Design*, 35(5):501–505, 2003.
- [7] Patrick Pastorelli, Simone Dagnino, Enrico Saccon, Marco Frego, and Luigi Palopoli. Fast shortest path polyline smoothing with g^1 continuity and bounded curvature, 2024.
- [8] Nathan Sturtevant. Benchmarks for Grid-Based Pathfinding. *Transactions on Computational Intelligence and AI in Games*, 4, 2012.
- [9] Ioan A. Șucan, Mark Moll, and Lydia E. Kavraki. The Open Motion Planning Library. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 19(4):72–82, December 2012. <https://ompl.kavrakilab.org>.
- [10] G.M. Zaverucha. Approximating polylines by curved paths. In *IEEE International Conference Mechatronics and Automation*, 2005, volume 2, pages 758–763 Vol. 2, 2005.